

DATA CHEAT SHEET FOR STUDENTS STAFF VISITORS

1. When is Research Data generated?

- Plan → Collect → Store → Analyze → Publish → Archive
- [Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#)

2. Responsibilities

- You are responsible for generating accurate data, maintenance, and creating proper documentation
- Report immediately any data issues
- [Responsibility at Aalto](#)

3. Storage spaces and Locations

- Storing research data in private devices is not advisable! (might lack security and backups)
- Use [VPN](#) when working outside of Aalto network
- [Data storage services at Aalto](#)
- **Students** and **Visitors** need to share their data with an authorized team member which then upload the data to the group storage. Requires to be agreed upon before starting

- **Personal** storages: spaces for personal material, such as work (drafts) or studies. Only the owner has access rights. Favored options and how to access them:

- Home: \\home.org.aalto.fi\userID
- Cloud [OneDrive](#): log in with your Aalto account to OneDrive and access 'My files'

- **Group** storage: shared space for all group members. Store all relevant research data in project-specific folders, uploading at least once a month. Access:

- (1) Log in [Microsoft Teams](#) with your Aalto account
- (2) Navigate to MMD team and then to your project space
- (3) Click on 'Files' tab
- (4) Link your workstation by clicking on ↻ Sync button

- **Department** storage: a storage for sharing information inside the unit (e.g., risk protocols). Ask for access

4. Organization of Group storage

- Each member is added to one or more projects
- Each project has the main structure:

`/Project/InProgress/FOLDER` → create subprojects ranging from organized testing ideas to potential publications (e.g., experimental data, proposals, collabs)

`/Project/Outputs/FOLDER` → add relevant outputs (e.g., presentations, photoshoots, guides, reports, thesis)

`/Project/Publications/FOLDER` → add all materials used in publications (e.g., drafts, figures, data sets)

- FOLDER naming conventions:
`YYYYMMDD_userID_DescriptiveName/`
- Each data set in FOLDER requires proper documentation. Bare minimum practice is a README file
- If possible, use open file formats for data storage

5. Space quotas

- Personal home space: 100 / 100 / 100 GB
- Personal cloud space: 50 / 100 / 10 GB

6. Sharing protocols

- The decision to share data lies with the PI
- When external collaborators are involved, follow security protocols and discuss beforehand collective [authorship](#) and ownership (research data is typically transferred to Aalto University)

7. Archiving

- Deletion period of Personal storage: 4 months
- Deletion of data of each project is to be defined case by case

8. Documentation

- Physical notebooks must be kept up to date and returned when leaving
- Digital notebooks: [amad.aalto.fi](#) is supported at Aalto and useful to store and analyse experiments data ([notebook.aalto.fi](#) is also supported but with less features)
- README files must contain at least:
 - (1) Outline the experiment
 - (2) Structure of data folders and how files names are organized
 - (3) Methodology
 - (4) Description of file formats
 - (5) Relevant metadata
- You can find examples of README files in the MMD Teams [General/Data Management/README](#) folder

9. Open Science

- All data used in publications that can be made open should be made open, following the principle *as open as possible, as closed as necessary*
- [Data availability statement](#)
- Use [Zenodo](#) to open data up to 50 GB

10. Training and Support

- [Access training materials](#)
- Support contacts: [Data Agents & IT Support](#)

11. Compliance and Policies

- For personnel with an Aalto contract, unless stated otherwise, the university holds unique database rights over research data, allowing it to decide on data use, access, and availability. As the author, you retain the right to receive credit and citations
- [Ethical Guidelines](#)
- [Institutional Policies on Open Science](#)
- [Legal Aid](#)